

Possibility of Propulsion Based on the Gravitational Effect of the Electromagnetic Field

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Let us assume that Newtonian gravitational theory is valid. Consider a rigid body, some parts of which possess continuously distributed excess charge. The charge distribution (describable by charge density) may vary in time. This charge distribution of the body generates an electric field, and a magnetic field may also arise. In a suitable medium (including vacuum), at an arbitrary point, the energy density of the electromagnetic field is:

$$u = \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon_0\varepsilon_r E^2 + \frac{1}{2\mu_0\mu_r} B^2, \quad (1)$$

where ε_0 is the vacuum permittivity, ε_r is the relative permittivity of the medium, μ_0 is the vacuum permeability, μ_r is the relative permeability of the medium. At this point, $E = |\vec{E}|$ is the magnitude of the electric field strength, and $B = |\vec{B}|$ is the magnitude of the magnetic induction. According to special relativity, the mass–energy equivalence holds, thus here the mass density of the electromagnetic field is:

$$\rho = \frac{u}{c^2}, \quad (2)$$

where c is the speed of light in vacuum.

The infinitesimal mass element of the electromagnetic field is:

$$dm = \rho dV, \quad (3)$$

where dV is the corresponding infinitesimal volume element.

Assume that the body is free of external constraints. Consider an arbitrary point in the medium, fixed with respect to the body, at which E and B can be controlled by appropriately modifying the charge distribution (charge density). According to the above equations, with fixed dV , dm can also be controlled. This implies that the resultant of the gravitational forces exerted by the electromagnetic field on the body can be controlled. Thus, the acceleration of the body's center of mass can also be controlled. The above gravitational forces acting on the body are to be regarded as external forces.

The possibility arises that this effect could be used for the propulsion of flying devices of a new kind.